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DEVELOPING STUDENTS' PROFESSIONAL COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN TEACHING ENGLISH THROUGH PROBLEM-BASED LEARNING TECHNOLOGY¹

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Abstract. The evolution of language education methodologies has necessitated the development of effective strategies that promote both linguistic proficiency and communicative competence. This article explores how Problem-Based Learning (PBL) technology can be utilized to develop students' professional communicative competence in teaching English. By examining the principles of PBL, its integration with language teaching, and its role in enhancing communicative skills, this paper offers a comprehensive understanding of how PBL serves as an innovative pedagogical tool. The study delves into the theoretical foundations of communicative competence, discusses PBL's application in English language teaching (ELT), and highlights the outcomes and challenges associated with this approach. This research aims to provide educators with insights into designing PBL-driven curricula that foster students' professional communicative competence, essential for effective language instruction in real-world contexts.

Keywords: language education, professional communicative competence, problem-based learning, innovative tool, language instruction.

Introduction. Professional communicative competence (PCC) in teaching English is a multifaceted skill set that integrates linguistic, sociolinguistic, strategic, and discourse competencies. It reflects an individual's ability to use language effectively and appropriately in a wide range of professional contexts [1]. As English continues to play a pivotal role in global communication, equipping students, especially future English language teachers, with the necessary skills to teach effectively is paramount. One promising approach for enhancing these skills is Problem-Based Learning (PBL) technology, a learner-centered

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instructional method that focuses on active problem-solving and real-world scenarios [2].

PBL technology encourages students to engage with authentic problems that require them to apply both theoretical knowledge and practical skills. In the context of language teaching, PBL can significantly enhance the development of communicative competence by providing students with opportunities to interact, collaborate, and reflect on their learning experiences. This article examines the theoretical underpinnings of PBL, its potential for fostering professional communicative competence in English language teaching, and the implications for curriculum design and teaching practice.

Professional Communicative Competence (PCC). The concept of communicative competence, introduced by sociolinguist Dell Hymes in the 1960s, has evolved into a central tenet of language education. It comprises four key components:

- Grammatical competence: The ability to produce and interpret grammatically correct sentences [9].
- Sociolinguistic competence: The capacity to use language appropriately based on social context, including factors like formality, register, and politeness [4].
- Discourse competence: The skill to produce coherent and cohesive texts in spoken or written forms [15].
- Strategic competence: The ability to employ strategies to overcome communication breakdowns and achieve communication goals, such as paraphrasing or using fillers [3].

In the context of teaching English, PCC goes beyond linguistic knowledge. It encompasses the ability to teach effectively, adapt language instruction to diverse learners, and communicate in a manner that promotes student engagement and learning. Teachers must be able to model effective communication, design communicative tasks, and foster a dynamic classroom environment conducive to language acquisition.

Problem-Based Learning Technology. Problem-Based Learning (PBL) is an educational methodology that originated in medical education in the 1960s. It is a student-

centered approach that encourages learning through solving real-world, complex problems. The core features of PBL include:

- Authentic, ill-structured problems: Problems that do not have straightforward solutions and require critical thinking and collaboration.
- Collaborative learning: Students work in groups to solve problems, share knowledge, and develop interpersonal skills.
- Self-directed learning: Students take responsibility for their learning, seeking out resources and developing independent learning strategies.
- Reflection: Students reflect on their learning process, helping them consolidate knowledge and skills [7].

In language teaching, PBL can be used to design tasks that simulate real-life teaching situations, where students are required to solve teaching-related problems. This encourages both linguistic and pedagogical development, ensuring that students gain practical experience in communicating effectively and managing classroom challenges.

Integrating PBL into English Language Teaching (ELT):

1. PBL and the Development of Communicative Competence

The integration of PBL technology into English language teaching offers several advantages in developing students' professional communicative competence:

- Contextualized language use: PBL tasks often require students to use English in context, engaging in discussions, presentations, and collaborative activities. This provides an authentic environment for practicing language use, thereby enhancing both linguistic and communicative skills.
- Collaborative problem-solving: Working in groups allows students to practice interpersonal communication, share ideas, and negotiate meaning. These interactions are key to developing strategic competence and sociolinguistic skills.
- Real-world application: PBL tasks simulate real-world teaching scenarios, such as designing

lesson plans, handling classroom management issues, or addressing learner needs. This allows students to hone their ability to communicate effectively in teaching situations, fostering their professional growth [5].

- Critical thinking and reflection: PBL encourages students to reflect on their learning process and the effectiveness of their communication strategies. This metacognitive aspect is essential for the development of strategic competence, enabling students to identify areas for improvement and adjust their communication approaches accordingly [11].

2. Curriculum Design for PBL in ELT

Incorporating PBL into the curriculum for teacher preparation programs requires a thoughtful approach to course design. Key considerations include:

- Selection of problems: The problems chosen for PBL tasks should be relevant to the students' future teaching contexts. For example, problems related to lesson planning, classroom management, or assessing students' language proficiency are highly applicable.
- Collaborative learning environments: Students should be encouraged to work in teams to solve problems. This promotes not only language development but also the development of teamwork and leadership skills, both essential in the teaching profession.
- Integration with existing curriculum: PBL should complement other aspects of teacher preparation, such as pedagogical theory, language acquisition research, and classroom management techniques. It should provide a platform for applying theoretical knowledge in a practical setting [6].
- Assessment of communicative competence: Assessment should focus on both linguistic and professional communicative skills. This may involve evaluating students' ability to present solutions to problems, collaborate with peers, and reflect on their performance in teaching contexts [12].

3. Practical Examples of PBL in ELT

To illustrate the application of PBL in developing communicative competence, the following examples can be considered:

- Task-based teaching design: Students could be given a problem where they need to design a lesson plan for a specific group of learners, addressing particular language skills. The group must discuss various teaching methods, consider the learners' needs, and present their lesson plan, justifying their choices based on pedagogical theory.
- Classroom management challenges: A problem could involve a classroom scenario where students need to resolve conflicts, deal with disruptive behavior, or manage diverse learner needs. Through collaboration, students would devise strategies and present them to the class.
- Assessment and feedback: Students could be tasked with evaluating a peer's language teaching and providing constructive feedback. This activity develops discourse competence, strategic competence, and sociolinguistic competence, as students must provide feedback that is both linguistically appropriate and professionally insightful [10].

Benefits of PBL for Developing PCC. The following points can be considered as the positive sides of problem-based learning:

- Enhanced Problem-Solving Skills: PBL encourages students to approach teaching challenges with creativity and critical thinking. This is particularly important for future teachers who must navigate diverse classroom environments and tailor their communication to various student needs.
- Improved Collaborative Skills: Through group work, students develop the ability to communicate with colleagues, share ideas, and negotiate solutions. These collaborative skills are crucial in professional teaching settings where teamwork and communication with peers and students are key to success.

- **Greater Autonomy and Responsibility:** PBL promotes self-directed learning, which is essential for developing lifelong learning habits. As students take ownership of their learning, they become more confident in their communicative abilities and better equipped to handle professional challenges.
- **Realistic Teaching Experience:** PBL tasks provide students with realistic scenarios that mirror the challenges they will face as teachers. This experiential learning helps bridge the gap between theory and practice, allowing students to develop professional competence in a supportive and dynamic environment [9].

Challenges in Implementing PBL for PCC Development. Problem-Based Learning (PBL) has emerged as a powerful pedagogical tool for fostering students' Professional Communicative Competence (PCC) across various disciplines, particularly in fields that require the application of communication skills, such as English language teaching (ELT). PBL is known for promoting collaborative learning, critical thinking, and the ability to solve complex, real-world problems. However, despite its potential, the implementation of PBL faces several challenges, particularly in the context of developing PCC.

PCC encompasses the knowledge, skills, and strategies necessary for effective communication in professional settings. In language teaching, it refers to a teacher's ability to communicate pedagogically, manage classroom interactions, and adapt language instruction to various contexts. PBL can be an effective means of developing these skills by simulating real-world teaching scenarios. However, implementing PBL in educational contexts is not without its difficulties. This article outlines the primary challenges that arise when utilizing PBL for PCC development, providing both theoretical and practical insights.

1. Time and Resource Constraints

One of the most significant challenges in implementing PBL is the time and resources required for its successful execution. Unlike traditional teaching methods, PBL involves in-depth research, collaboration, and problem-solving, which can be time-consuming for both students and instructors. The open-ended nature of PBL problems

requires substantial preparation, both in terms of designing meaningful problems and providing students with adequate guidance throughout the learning process [13]. For students, PBL necessitates extensive self-directed learning and group work, which can be overwhelming without proper time management. Instructors must also devote considerable time to facilitating discussions, monitoring group dynamics, and providing feedback. This can be particularly challenging in large classes, where managing individual student progress and fostering productive group collaboration becomes more complex. In addition, PBL often requires access to diverse resources, including research materials, technology, and collaborative platforms. Educational institutions may not always have the necessary infrastructure to support such an approach. For example, the lack of access to digital tools or an insufficient number of collaborative spaces can hinder students' ability to fully engage with PBL activities, thereby limiting its effectiveness in developing PCC.

2. Student Resistance and Lack of Preparedness

Implementing PBL may encounter resistance from students who are accustomed to more traditional, teacher-centered pedagogies. In many educational systems, students are familiar with lectures, exams, and a more structured, content-driven approach to learning. As a result, the shift to a PBL model, which emphasizes active learning, collaboration, and problem-solving, can be met with reluctance. Some students may struggle with the lack of structure and clarity that often accompanies PBL. For example, they may find it difficult to take responsibility for their own learning and may prefer the more passive role that traditional teaching methods offer. In language teaching contexts, where communicative competence is emphasized, students might feel insecure about engaging in collaborative problem-solving tasks, fearing they will be judged based on their language proficiency or interpersonal communication skills. These anxieties can inhibit participation and hinder the development of PCC. Moreover, PBL demands strong self-regulation skills, including the ability to manage time effectively, work independently, and seek out additional resources. Students who lack these skills may struggle to navigate PBL tasks successfully, which could undermine their ability to develop the communicative competence required for professional settings.

3. Assessment Complexities

Assessing students' Professional Communicative Competence (PCC) in PBL is particularly challenging due to the multifaceted nature of communication skills. PCC involves not only linguistic proficiency but also the ability to adapt language use to different professional contexts, manage interactions, and navigate cultural and social factors in communication. Evaluating these skills requires a comprehensive approach to assessment, which can be difficult to implement in PBL settings. Traditional assessment methods, such as exams or quizzes, may not adequately capture the nuanced development of PCC. Instead, assessment in PBL needs to be more holistic and formative, focusing on both the process (e.g., how students collaborate, communicate, and reflect) and the product (e.g., the solutions or outcomes of the problem-solving tasks). This requires instructors to develop complex rubrics that account for a wide range of competencies, including critical thinking, interpersonal communication, and the ability to apply theoretical knowledge in real-world contexts. Furthermore, assessing group-based work in PBL introduces additional complexities. Evaluating the contributions of individual students within a collaborative setting can be challenging, especially if group dynamics are not well-managed. Instructors must ensure that assessments are fair and transparent, taking into account both the collective outcomes of group work and the individual efforts of each student. Without clear and well-designed assessment frameworks, students may feel uncertain about how their PCC development is being evaluated, leading to confusion and frustration.

4. Instructor Expertise and Preparedness

Effective implementation of PBL requires instructors who are not only skilled in the content they teach but also proficient in managing the dynamics of a student-centered, collaborative learning environment. Facilitating PBL requires a shift from traditional teaching roles, as instructors become more of guides or facilitators rather than lecturers [8]. This demands strong interpersonal skills, the ability to promote critical thinking, and a deep understanding of how to support students in problem-solving processes. Many instructors, particularly those trained in traditional pedagogical methods, may lack the experience or training

needed to successfully implement PBL. They may struggle with managing group work, providing timely and effective feedback, or balancing the needs of individual students with the overall objectives of the problem-solving tasks. Moreover, instructors may feel uncertain about how to assess and evaluate students' performance in PBL settings, especially when it comes to assessing PCC. The lack of professional development opportunities for instructors in PBL methodologies can hinder its successful implementation. Educators need training in how to design and facilitate PBL tasks effectively, as well as how to create a learning environment that encourages collaboration, problem-solving, and communication. Instructors who are not well-prepared may inadvertently create barriers to student success, undermining the potential benefits of PBL for PCC development.

5. Classroom and Institutional Constraints

Implementing PBL for PCC development is also influenced by the broader classroom and institutional context. Instructors may face constraints such as large class sizes, limited class time, and insufficient institutional support. PBL is particularly resource-intensive, requiring adequate space for group work, access to research materials, and the ability to provide individualized attention to students. In overcrowded classrooms, it can be difficult to facilitate meaningful group discussions and monitor the progress of each student [14]. Moreover, some institutions may not be fully committed to student-centered pedagogies like PBL, favoring traditional, content-driven methods instead. Institutional support is crucial for creating the necessary infrastructure and providing the resources required to implement PBL effectively. Without this support, instructors may struggle to integrate PBL into their courses, limiting its impact on PCC development.

While Problem-Based Learning (PBL) offers a promising approach to developing Professional Communicative Competence (PCC) in language teaching [3], its implementation presents a range of challenges. Time and resource constraints, student resistance, assessment complexities, instructor expertise, and institutional limitations all contribute to the difficulties associated with adopting PBL in educational settings. To overcome these challenges, institutions must provide the necessary resources,

support, and professional development opportunities for both students and instructors. Instructors must also develop the skills needed to facilitate PBL effectively and assess PCC development in a meaningful way [17]. Despite these challenges, the benefits of PBL—such as fostering critical thinking, collaboration, and real-world problem-solving skills—make it a valuable approach to developing communicative competence in future educators. By addressing the challenges outlined in this article, educators can ensure that PBL becomes an effective tool for promoting PCC development in language teaching contexts.

Conclusion. Problem-Based Learning technology offers a dynamic and effective approach to developing students' professional communicative competence in teaching English. By engaging students in authentic, problem-solving tasks, PBL fosters a deeper understanding of language teaching and equips future educators with the communicative skills necessary for success in diverse professional contexts. The integration of PBL into teacher preparation programs provides an innovative pedagogical framework that supports the development of both linguistic proficiency and professional competence, ultimately contributing to more effective and reflective English language teachers. As the field of language teaching continues to evolve, it is crucial for educators and curriculum designers to embrace methodologies like PBL that not only enhance students' academic knowledge but also prepare them for the communicative demands of the professional world.

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